

Applications of microwave in chemical science and metallurgical activities

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Microwave (MW) is a type of electromagnetic (EM) radiation with a wavelength ranging from 1 meter to 1 millimeter and frequency ranging from 3 to 300 GHz. These waves are used for a large number of applications like point to point telecommunication, Global Positioning System (GPS), RADAR, heating and spectroscopy. One of the pioneering areas of research is the application of MWs in spectroscopy, such as Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) Spectroscopy, which provides information on unpaired electrons in a chemical system, such as free radicals or transition metal ions. Besides this, the use of MWs has been extensive in chemical science because of its heating effect obtained at low cost. The effect of heating is created by the interaction of the permanent dipole moment of the molecule with high-frequency EM radiation. Results of experiments on MW-assisted organic synthesis have consistently shown significant acceleration of reaction rate, not possible by classical heating methods. Benefits like rapid volumetric heating, suppressed side reactions, with minimized energy loss and energy saving have been obtained on MW-assisted reactions. The research and application of MW radiation have become ubiquitous in research on almost all fields of chemistry. Some of these reactions include hydrogenation of alkenes, degradation of polychlorinated hydrocarbons and hydrocracking of bitumen from tar sands. Apart from chemical science, pioneering efforts have been reported on application of MWs for in the fields of mineral processing by way of selective heating of minerals to reduce the cost of size reduction. Encouraging results have been reported on the MW-assisted selective heating in Pyrometallurgy with faster reduction and in hydrometallurgical leaching, yielding more rapid dissolution of metallic cations. This paper reviews the various applications of MWs in the above-mentioned fields of chemical science and metallurgy.

Keywords: MW energy in metallurgy, heat transfer limitations, waste management, leaching.

Introduction

MWs are a type of electromagnetic radiation with a wavelength ranging from 1 mm to 1 m, and frequency ranging from 3 GHz to 300 GHz¹⁻⁵. MWs travel by line of sight, unlike the other lower frequency radiowaves, they do not travel as ground waves which follow the contour of earth⁶. The main high power sources for MWs are specialized vacuum tubes to generate MWs. These devices operate on different principles ranging from low-frequency vacuum tubes, which use high-speed electrons in a vacuum under the influence of controlling electric and magnetic fields. These include the magnetron (used in MW ovens), klystron, travelling-wave tube (TWT). Low power MW sources use solid state devices such as field-effect transistors, tunnel diodes, Gunn diodes⁷. All warm objects emit low-level MW black body radiation, depending on their temperature. Hence, the remote sensing

techniques use this phenomenon to find the temperatures of the distant objects⁸.

MWs are used for point to point communication links, wireless networks, MW radio relay networks, RADAR, satellite and space craft communication links, wireless networks, MW radio relay networks, radio astronomy, particle accelerators, spectroscopy, industrial heating, collision avoidance systems, garage door openers⁹⁻¹⁴. Recently, a lot of papers on the applications of MWs in science, particularly in chemical science and metallurgical science have come out. The biggest advantage of using MW radiation is that the heating rate is very fast¹⁵. MWs act as high-frequency electric fields and will generally heat any material containing mobile electric charges, such as polar molecules in a solvent or conducting ions in a solid¹⁶. Polar solvents are heated as their component molecules are forced to rotate with the field and

lose energy in collisions. Acting as an internal heat source, MW absorption is able to heat the target compounds without heating the entire furnace or oil bath, which saves time and energy¹⁷.

In this article, we shall elaborate various applications of MWs in the chemical sciences and metallurgical sciences. The applications that will be discussed include the application of MWs in organic synthesis including hydrogenation of alkenes, degradation of polychlorinated hydrocarbons and hydrocracking from sands. In metallurgical sciences, its major application area is mineral processing, which further comprises of MWs assisted ore grinding, MW-assisted pre-treatment of refractory gold concentrate, MW-assisted reduction of metal oxide, MW-assisted drying and hydration and MW-assisted waste management and nanocrystalline materials.

Application of MW in Chemical Science

In the background of green chemistry, MW irradiation provides an alternative to the conventional methods, for heating or introducing energy into the system. It utilizes the ability of mobile electric charges present in liquid or conducting ions in solid to transform electromagnetic energy into heat. MW-assisted reactions are fast, clean, economic and eco-friendly and this technique has been proposed as the "technology of tomorrow". It has emerged as a valuable alternative in the organic compounds, polymers, inorganic materials, and nanomaterials. Important innovations in MW-assisted chemistry now enable chemists to prepare catalytic materials or nanomaterials and desired organic molecules, selectively, in almost quantitative yields and with greater precision than using conventional heating. Hence, in the upcoming discussion, we are going to shed light on the application of organic and inorganic materials synthesis using MW technology.

Organic synthesis

MW ovens have been used in chemical laboratories for moisture analysis and wet ashing procedures of biological and geological materials for a number of years¹⁸⁻²¹. Very recently the rapid heating capability of the MW oven has been exploited to heat mixtures of ore samples and acid in sealed vessels, leading to considerable savings in dissolution times. The applications of MW technology to the catalytic hydrogenation of alkenes, the hydrocracking of bitumen from tar sands and the degradation of polychlorinated hydrocarbons are all currently under intensive investigation²².

Organic synthesis under pressure using MW ovens

The results of several experiments in which organic reactions have been carried out in sealed Teflon vessels heated by a MW oven have been discussed. The high temperatures and pressures so readily obtained in the reaction vessels have led to remarkable rate enhancements and dramatic savings in reaction times.

Richard Gedye, Frank Smith *et al.*²² studied four completely different types of organic reactions and which were: (i) the acid hydrolysis of benzamide to give benzoic acid; (ii) the permanganate oxidation of toluene in basic solution giving benzoic acid; (iii) the esterification of benzoic acid with methanol, propanol and butanol, and (iv) the SN2 reaction between sodium 4-cyanophenoxide and benzyl chloride, yielding 4-cyanophenyl benzyl ether. Each reaction was carried out both under traditional reflux conditions, and also in a sealed Teflon vessel in a MW oven. The microwave oven used in these experiments was a domestic Toshiba model ER-8000BTC with nine power settings, starting at 72 watts and increasing by 81-watt increments to 720 watts. The Teflon vessels used for the MW reactions had a volume of 250 ml (approx) and were manufactured by Berghof/America Inc. The quantities of reactants, and their concentrations were kept the same under both sets of reaction conditions.

In the MW oven experiments, very significant rate enhancements were obtained for all the reactions. As would be expected, those occurring in a low-boiling solvent were affected most dramatically. Thus, if we consider the two reactions taking place in methanol, the esterification of benzoic acid proceeds almost one hundred times as fast in the MW oven as under reflux, while the synthesis of 4-cyanophenyl ether is accomplished with a rate enhancement of about two hundred and forty times. The reaction in propanol, the next lowest-boiling solvent, displays a twenty-five fold rate increase in the MW oven. The hydrolysis of benzamide, which is carried out in aqueous solution, proceeds six times faster in the MW oven. The other reaction in aqueous solution, the oxidation of toluene, shows a five-fold rate enhancement, even though the system is heterogeneous. Unfortunately, when longer reaction times were employed in an attempt to reach completion, dangerously high pressures developed under the MW oven conditions, resulting in a violent explosion. Further investigation of this system was therefore abandoned. The highest-boiling solvent used, n-butanol, showed an eightfold

rate enhancement in the esterification of benzoic acid. This inverse relationship between rate enhancement and the boiling point of the solvent is especially clearly demonstrated in the series of esterifications.

Cross-coupling reactions

MW heating in the aqueous medium is found to be advantageous for C–C coupling reactions such as the Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction. Ley *et al.*²³ have reported a rapid MW-assisted Sonogashira cross-coupling of aryl iodides and bromides with terminal alkynes using reusable Pd-EnCatTM TPP30 (encapsulated Pd with PPh₃) catalysts. Various aryl bromides and iodides, as well as heteroaryl species, underwent coupling reactions with substituted terminal alkynes to afford the corresponding coupled products, in moderate to excellent yields. Qu *et al.*²⁴ reported Suzuki-Miyaura reaction of nucleosides, 6-chloropurines, with arylation reagent, sodium tetraarylborate, in neat water. Unprotected 6-chloropurine nucleoside, however, gave the C–N glycosidic bond cleaved product both in water and in ethanol. The aforementioned magnetite-Glu-Cu catalyst proved useful for the coupling of aryl halides with thiophenols under MW-irradiation conditions. Along similar lines, a benign protocol for Heck-type arylation of alkenes and diaryliodonium salts on magnetically retrievable Pd nanocatalysts has been developed via functionalization of magnetite with dopamine (magnetite-dopa-Pd)²⁵.

The results obtained convincingly demonstrate that the use of this MW oven technique can lead to substantial savings in time for many laboratory synthesis, particularly those involving low-boiling solvents or reagents. The method provides rapid and relatively inexpensive access to very high temperatures and pressures. The currently available alternatives require much more elaborate apparatus, longer heating times, and allow virtually no control over energy input.

Inorganic synthesis

MW-assisted synthesis of inorganic nanomaterials and the use of nanocatalysts are growing rapidly. Inorganic nanomaterials include diverse classes of functional materials, namely, metals, metal oxides, sulfides, phosphates, and halides. Selected examples of nanoparticles are documented here to underline the versatility of the MW-assisted approach for accessing a variety of nanomaterials. Discussion regarding the synthesis of MgO nanoparticles is done followed by synthesis of Ag nanoparticles using glycerol.

Synthesis of MgO nanoparticles

Of the many methods employed today for the fabrication of nanomaterials, the use of MW radiation is the one which requires the smallest investment in equipment, since it can be carried out in domestic MW oven. The effect of heating in MWs is created by the interaction of the permanent dipole moment with high frequency (2456 MHz) Electromagnetic Radiation. The ability of any material to absorb MW is expressed by its dielectric loss factor. One of the pioneering attempts has been manufacture of nanoparticles²⁶. They synthesized MgO nanoparticles in a MW oven, where Mg(CH₃COO)₂, is dissolved in ethylene glycol, was decomposed yielding amorphous nanoparticles of Mg(OH)₂. The conversion rate was very high and 95% of the Mg(CH₃COO)₂ was converted to Mg(OH)₂ nanoparticles. The particles were annealed at 600°C. The concentration of Mg²⁺ in the mother liquid was determined by the titration method and using EDTA (Ethylene Diammine Tetra Acetate) as a titrant. The concentration was found to be 5×10⁻⁵ M. The characterization of these particles confirmed the presence of Mg(OH)₂ particles. The nanoscale nature of the annealed compound can be confirmed by finding its specific Surface Area using Braunaeur Emmett Reller (BET) technique, which yielded a value of 118 m² g⁻¹. The feasibility of this technique to synthesize other nanocrystals is being investigated. However, this technique if implemented on a large scale would revolutionize the nanoparticle synthesis technique due to its cost effectiveness.

Nanoparticle synthesis using glycerol

Glycerol, an abundant and safe by product from biodiesel production, has garnered attention as an alternative sustainable solvent for catalytic reactions and nanomaterials synthesis because of its unique physical and chemical properties, such as high polarity, low toxicity, high boiling point, and biodegradability.

Diameter-controlled Ag nanowires were fabricated using inexpensive and biodegradable solvent glycerol, which serves as both reductant and solvent under nonstirred MW irradiation conditions. When the amount of sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) used was low, bundles of Ag nanowires were obtained, while unbundled Ag nanowires were formed with a higher SDS amount. The thickness of the obtained Ag nanowires can be controlled by adjusting the relative amounts of glycerol and AgNO₃.

The viability of this greener approach using glycerol has been established for the fabrication of Au, Pt, and Pd nanomaterials under MW irradiation conditions. Surfactants, such as cetyltriethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and SDS, are employed for the syntheses of noble metal nanoparticles with different morphologies. In the presence of CTAB, Au nanosheets were formed within 2 min, and the size of the nanosheet can be controlled by glycerol content and MW irradiation time. The shapes of ensuing particles can be altered by the addition of various surfactants²⁶.

Application of MW in metallurgical activities

Metallurgical activities are highly energy intensive. This energy mostly comes from the conventional sources like fossil fuels. This leads to a lot of pollution including the release of certain harmful gases like carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, oxides of nitrogen and sulphur. This makes them highly unsustainable for future use. MW heating can be a very suitable alternative for the conventional fossil fuel. Here, in this section, we shall look at the various applications of MW in different subdivisions of metallurgy like Mineral Processing, Pyrometallurgy, and Hydrometallurgy.

Mineral processing and extraction

Mineral processing in the field of extractive metallurgy, also known as ore dressing, is the process of separating commercially valuable minerals from their ores. It is the first process that most ores undergo after mining in order to provide a more concentrated material for the procedures of extractive metallurgy. The primary operations are comminution and concentration, but there are other important operations in a modern mineral processing plant, including sampling and analysis and dewatering. The processes involved require a large amount of energy in the form of heat. MW can serve as an alternative source of energy for carrying out those processes, which are further discussed in detail.

Drying and anhydration

Generally, drying in technical term means removal of physically adsorbed solvents such as water, acids or high vapor pressure organic substances, e.g. alcohol, acetone, ether. On the other hand, anhydration refers to the removal of water, chemically bound to a substance present intermolecular as well as the intramolecular elimination of water from hydroxyl or carboxyl compounds. If both the solvent and the substance are to be dried are transparent to the MW (i.e. no heating occurs) then suitable MW heat accelerators such as

carbon, magnetite or silicon carbide must be added to the system to heat the added material to volatilize the solvent.

Haque²⁷ experimented on anhydration and revealed that MW heating can remove water from hydrated magnesium chloride ($\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and convert goethite ($\text{O}=\text{Fe}-\text{OH}$) into haematite (Fe_2O_3).

Mineral processing

The vast majority of metal oxides and carbon itself responds to the MW heating. Hence, a large number of experiments have been conducted to examine the effect of carbothermic reductions in the presence of a MW environment. To compare the conventional and MW reduction; Standish *et al.*²⁸ conducted reduction tests on identical sample mixtures of Haematite ore fines, Coke and Lime Powder. A sample of each mixture was heated in an electrical muffle furnace at 1000°C and in 2450 MHz MW oven at the power of 1.3 KW. The sample temperature was measured with a thermocouple inserted in the sample and the test was terminated, when the temperature reached 1000°C. The MW heating rate was found to be much higher than the conventional heating rate. Standish *et al.*²⁸ concluded on the basis of the above observations that the MW reduction process could save 15%–50% of the energy as compared to the conventional sources.

Conventional heat treatment of heating the ores and minerals to facilitate crushing and grinding operations is a highly energy-intensive process. Hence, researchers started searching for a more sustainable way on the application of MW in mineral processing. Several works including one of the famous work of Chen *et al.*²⁹ in 1984, explored the possibility of heating of minerals prior to size reduction. It had been observed conclusively that MW heat some minerals selectively as compared to others. This selective behaviour has been attributed to the dielectric properties of different minerals which govern the proportion of the input energy dissipated as heat. Minerals containing ferrous compounds are found to be heated more by microwaves as compared to the non-ferrous minerals. From a large number of minerals tested, it was noted that most silicates, carbonates, sulphates and some oxides are transparent to MWs, while sulphides, arsenides, sulfosalts heat well when subjected to MW irradiation³⁰.

Most recently, the US Bureau of Mines³¹ revealed that the highest temperatures were attained for carbon and most

of the metal oxides such as NiO, MnO₂, Co₂O₃. Most metal sulphides are heated well but the gangue minerals such as quartz, Calcite, and Feldspar did not heat significantly. The MWs, generated sufficient thermal stress because of uneven heating to produce microcracks on the surface of the ore, hence, grinding and crushing become easier.

Overall, it was observed that the grinding process which consumes about 50 percent of the total energy consumed in mineral processing operations could be improved up to 23%³². In summary, MW-assisted grinding is most effective when the MW absorbing minerals (metal oxides, sulphide ores etc.), which absorb MW and convert to heat are encased in gangue minerals which allow MWs to pass through, i.e. which are transparent to MWs (silicates, carbonates, sulphates and some oxides)³³.

Pyrometallurgy

Pyrometallurgy is one of the most energy-intensive processes for metal processing. Moreover, the efficiency of the process is very poor due to the poor thermal conductivity of the raw materials. MW heating helps to overcome these challenges, as the heating is in bulk and not only through the surface. In this section, we shall go through the applications of MWs in major pyrometallurgical processes like Carbothermic reduction of Oxides. Then, we shall look at the specific case of ilmenite. This would be subsequently followed by extending the applications to management of waste generated during pyrometallurgical operations.

MW-assisted carbothermic reduction of metal oxides

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Treatment of ilmenite

Iron can be extracted preferentially to yield titanium rich product from Ilmenite. This can be very useful in the production of TiO₂. MW heating was compared with conventional heating. It was found that reduction temperature was reached quickly with MW heating. This led to the conclusion that using MWs to promote rapid heating while using a cheaper energy source to maintain temperature. Iron extraction efficiency was found to be higher in the conventional source of heating. However, conventional reduction required 4 to 8 hours as opposed to 10 min using MWs.

Waste management

The huge amount of gases generated during steel making, petroleum extraction, mining industry and other major pyrometallurgical processes consists of NO_x and SO_x. These gases are responsible for causing acid rains and breathing problems such as Nausea. Cha³⁵ demonstrated that in laboratory scales SO₂ and NO_x in industrial flue gas can be decomposed into elemental nitrogen and sulphur and a mixture of carbon-dioxide and carbon monoxide. The first step of the process involves passing off the flue gas containing SO₂ and NO_x through a column packed with activated carbon to absorb the toxic gases. The loaded carbon column is then heated by MWs and the resulting CO, CO₂ and N₂ is released into the atmosphere.

H₂S is another very toxic gas produced from the petroleum refineries. Conventional hydrogen sulphide is treated using the Claus process; which is based on partial oxidation of hydrogen sulphide into sulphur (S) and water (H₂O). The Kurchatov Institute of Moscow, Russia developed a process for the decomposition of hydrogen sulphide into hydrogen and sulphur by applying a MW plasma (Plasmatron). Similar investigations by the Argon National Laboratory (ANL) of the USA developed³⁶ a plasma-chemical waste stream process in which H₂S waste stream is passed through a MW generated plasma reactor where it's decomposed into hydrogen and sulphur. The energy and economic sustainability of the process are commendable.

Hydrometallurgy

Hydrometallurgy is a technique within the field of extractive metallurgy involving the use of aqueous chemistry for the

recovery of metals from ores, concentrates, and recycled or residual materials. Heating is essential in the hydrometallurgy process to optimize the rate, extent, and selectivity of dissolution of the desired metal component into the aqueous phase. Hence, the use of MWs for the heating purpose is novel and is less known among metallurgists at present. Here, we have shed light upon the MW assisted leaching of minerals and the MW assisted leaching of gold refractory concentrate.

MW-assisted direct leaching/reduction

Nickel in a laterite ore could be leached with a 25 vol.% sulphuric acid solution under MW irradiation (245 GHz, 600 W) within 1.5 h. When the leaching temperature was 90°C, approximately 90.8% of Ni was recovered. The kinetic analysis showed that the leaching process was controlled by the chemical reaction occurring on the surface of samples, and the apparent activation energy was 38.9 kJ per mole. MW-assisted leaching promoted dissolution of laterite ores compared with conventional thermal conductive heating, such as water bath heating. As expected, the leaching process depended on the leaching agents and temperature. When MW radiation was applied directly to the leaching slurry containing sulphuric and hydrochloric acids for recovering Ni and Co from their ores with a high content of Mg, the metal extraction increased substantially in comparison with conventional leaching at temperatures between 230 and 250°C³⁷.

Peng and Liu³⁸ applied MW energy in the leaching of sphalerite with acidic ferric chloride. Various parameters such as particle size and ferric chloride concentration were studied. Test results demonstrated that leaching rate of zinc increased with increase in temperature in both MW and conventional heating systems. Then, they reported 90% zinc extraction when the leach concentrations were at 0.1 M, 1.0 M FeCl₃, 60 min heating time and temperature of 95°C. Under similar conditions, conventional leaching yielded only 50% zinc extraction. The process indicates that it has the potential for annual savings of 40 to 70 trillion Btu or \$500 to \$1000 millions for refining industries³⁹.

Pre-treatment of refractory gold concentrate

Gold is considered to be refractory if it cannot be easily recovered by alkaline – cyanide leaching. The vast majority of refractory gold occurs in sulphidic minerals such as pyrite

(FeS₂) and Arsenopyrite (FeAsS). Generally, refractory gold concentrate or ore is pre-treated by roasting, oxidative-pressure leaching or bacterial leaching to make it suitable for alkaline cyanide recovery. Haque⁴⁰ conducted a laboratory scale MW pre-treatment test on Arsenopyrite gold concentrate. More than 80% of As and S were volatilized as As₂O₃ and SO₂, whereas Fe was oxidized to haematite at 550°C. Alkaline cyanide treatment of MW-treated ore yielded 98% of the total Au and 60% of the total Ag.

To avoid the formation of As₂O₃ and SO₂, the author conducted the test in nitrogen atmosphere.

This paper deals with the extraction of gold ores containing both sulphides and carbonaceous matter. This type of ores is referred to as double refractory gold ores. However, the presence of these carbonaceous matters makes direct MW heating difficult, because of their poor MW absorption. Hence, instead of using direct MW heating, indirect MW heating has been used. Magnetite has been used as the susceptor for indirect MW roasting, with significant gold recovery as high as 98%.

Summary

MW heating processes are currently undergoing investigation for application in a number of fields. The advantages of MW energy may lead to significant savings in energy consumption, process time and environmental remediation. For chemical synthesis, the deviations from conventional heating provide opportunities to enhance the utility of MW heating above current practices, perhaps leading to reduced energy costs of reactions and processes, refined and/or altered reaction pathways and equilibria, and may be even identification of new modes of reactivity unique to MW heating. MW-assisted organic synthesis has advantages over conventional technology: it is more energy efficient and it can lead to improved isolated yields of products. The advantages of this enabling technology have also been exploited in the context of multistep total synthesis and medicinal chemistry/drug discovery and have additionally penetrated related fields such as polymer synthesis, nanotechnology, and biochemical processes. In case of application of MW in metallurgy, although there is still much work ahead for advancing its understanding and application, the use of MW energy in extractive metallurgy represents a very promising technology that can

achieve commercialization and industrialization provided proper measures are taken from technical and scientific perspectives. In case of pyrometallurgical processes, the MW radiation can overcome, to some extent, the heat transfer limitations of the oxide ores, which arise mainly from their low thermal conductivities. In the future, tremendous progress in both materials science and MW engineering can be expected.

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